

TABLE 1—THIOSEMICARBAZONES OF TYPE

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Antitubercular activity at 25.0 µg/ml
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	175	—
2.	-2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	165	—
3.	-5-Br-2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	158	—
4.	3,5-diBr-2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	180	—
5.	-2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	219	—
6.	-4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	146	—
7.	-3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	161	—
8.	-4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	220	—
9.	-C ₆ H ₄ O	216	—
10.	-4-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	179	—

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N, S analysis.

TABLE 2—1,3,4-THIADIAZOLINES OF TYPE

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	218
2.	-2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	200
3.	-5-Br-2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	178
4.	3,5-diBr-2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	above 360
5.	-2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	238
6.	-4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	195
7.	-3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	203
8.	-4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	242
9.	-C ₆ H ₄ O	200
10.	-4-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	210

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N, S analysis. The above compounds show some antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

Mycobacterium tuberculosis in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media (4 ml) at 5.00 µg/ml and 25.00 µg/ml concentrations of the test substances (solvent-acetone). The retardation of growth has been studied upto six weeks at 37°.

(c) Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity have been tested by nutrient agar pour plate method in DMF and the compounds are found active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in various concentrations.

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Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Substituted 4-Thiazolidinones and Their Benzoyl Derivatives

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives have been found to possess wide variety of physiological properties¹⁻⁷. With a view to prepare better therapeutic agents, we have synthesised 4-thiazolidinones of type (I) containing nitrophenol residue, by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid or thiomalic acid on Schiff bases which were obtained by condensing 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-3-nitro-benzophenone⁸ with different sulpha drugs. The structure was supported by ir spectra⁹⁻¹².

R = H, pyrimidyl, 4'-methylpyrimidyl-4',6'-dimethyl pyrimidyl, 2'-thiazolyl or 3,4'-dimethyl oxazolyl.

R₁ = H, OH, -CH₂COOH
R₂ = H, COO₆H₅

IR spectra :

The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones of type (I) were taken on KBr pellets and characterised. The ν(-C=O) group frequency was obtained at 1635 cm⁻¹, ν(N-CO) at 1585 cm⁻¹ ν(phenolic OH) at 341 cm⁻¹ and ν(NHSO₂) at 1155 cm⁻¹. The reported frequencies are ν(-C=O) at 1655-1760 cm⁻¹, ν(N-CO) at 1580 cm⁻¹, ν(NHSO₂) at 1140-1160 cm⁻¹ and ν(phenolic OH) at 300-340 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

(1) Preparation of α-phenyl-5-chloro-2-hydroxy-3-nitro benzalanil/2-benzoate : 5-Chloro-2-hydroxy-3-nitro benzophenone (0.01 mole) dissolved in ethanol was added to sulphanilamide (0.01 mole in ethanol) and refluxed on water bath for 6 hr. The

contents were poured into water and the product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. The anils were benzoylated in the usual way and crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow needles, (when $R_2=H$) m.p. 105°, yield 70%. (Found : C, 52.80 ; H, 3.21 ; N, 9.68. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{14}O_5N_3SCl$; C, 52.84 ; H, 3.24 ; N, 9.73%).

Other anils were prepared similarly (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND ANTIMICROBIAL DATA OF ANILS

Sl. No.	R	R_2	m.p. °C
1.	H	H	105
2.	H	C_6H_5CO	125
3.	Pyrimidyl	H	145
4.	Pyrimidyl	C_6H_5CO	165
5.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	H	180
6.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	C_6H_5CO	190
7.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	125
8.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	C_6H_5CO	170
9.	2'-Thiazolyl	H	205
10.	2'-Thiazolyl	C_6H_5CO	196
11.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	H	150
12.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	C_6H_5CO	176

(2) Preparation of α -phenyl-2-(5'-chloro-3'-hydroxy-3'-nitro phenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-4-thiazolidinone : α -Phenyl-5-chloro-2-hydroxy-3-nitro benzal anil (0.01 mole) in benzene was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.01 mole) on water bath for 4 hr. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 120°, yield 59%. (Found : C, 49.81 ; H, 3.11 ; N, 8.25. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{16}O_6N_3S_2Cl$; C, 49.85 ; H, 3.17 ; N, 8.31%).

Similarly, other anils were treated with thioglycolic acid (Table 2).

(3) Preparation of α -phenyl-2'-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-3'-nitrophenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone : Thiolactic acid (0.01 mole) was added to a saturated solution α -phenyl-5-chloro-2-hydroxy-3-nitro benzal anil (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 hr. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol as brown needles, m.p. 130°, yield 60%. (Found : C, 50.81 ; H, 3.41 ; N, 8.03. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{18}O_6N_3S_2Cl$; C, 50.82 ; H, 3.46 ; N, 8.08%).

Similarly, other anils were treated with thiolactic acid (Table 2).

(4) Preparation of α -phenyl-2-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-3'-nitrophenyl)-3-o-amino sulphophenyl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone : α -Phenyl-5-chloro-3-hydroxy-3-nitro benzyl anil (0.01 mole) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mole) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 30 min (Reddelien method)¹⁸. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitated with acid and crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow needles, m.p. 120°, yield 65%. (Found : C, 48.98 ; H, 3.19 ; N, 7.42. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{18}O_8N_3S_2Cl$; C, 48.93 ; H, 3.14 ; N, 7.42%).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANT AND ANTIMICROBIAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONE OF TYPE (I)

Sl. No.	R	R_1	R_2	m.p. °C
1.	H	H	H	125
2.	H	H	C_6H_5CO	140
3.	H	OH_2	H	130
4.	H	OH_2	C_6H_5CO	180
5.	H	CH_2COOH	H	120
6.	H	CH_2COOH	C_6H_5CO	115
7.	Pyrimidyl	H	H	150
8.	Pyrimidyl	H	C_6H_5CO	185
9.	Pyrimidyl	OOH_2	H	180
10.	Pyrimidyl	CH_2	C_6H_5CO	195
11.	Pyrimidyl	CH_2COOH	H	160
12.	Pyrimidyl	CH_2COOH	C_6H_5CO	182
13.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	H	H	210
14.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	H	C_6H_5CO	226
15.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	CH_2	H	215
16.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	CH_2	C_6H_5CO	218
17.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	CH_2COOH	H	206
18.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	CH_2COOH	C_6H_5CO	220
19.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	H	139
20.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	C_6H_5CO	180
21.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	CH_2	H	140
22.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	CH_2	C_6H_5CO	185
23.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	CH_2COOH	H	135
24.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	CH_2COOH	C_6H_5CO	178
25.	2'-Thiazolyl	H	H	215
26.	2'-Thiazolyl	H	C_6H_5CO	205
27.	2'-Thiazolyl	CH_2	H	210
28.	2'-Thiazolyl	CH_2	C_6H_5CO	225
29.	2'-Thiazolyl	CH_2COOH	H	218
30.	2'-Thiazolyl	CH_2COOH	C_6H_5CO	216
31.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	H	H	165
32.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	H	C_6H_5CO	185
33.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	CH_2	H	160
34.	3',4'-Dimethyl	CH_2	C_6H_5CO	189
35.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	CH_2COOH	H	169
36.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	CH_2COOH	C_6H_5CO	182

All compounds gave consistent elemental analysis ; yield was between 52-75%.

Similarly, other anils were treated with thiomalic acid (Table 2).

Antimicrobial screening :

The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup plate method¹ using *S. aureus* (gram +ve) and *E. coli* (gram -ve). The testing was carried out in ethanol solution at a concentration 10 mg/ml. The zone of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) was recorded.

Most of the anils and their 4-thiazolidinone derivatives are active against gram positive bacteria only. Moreover, 4-thiazolidinone, where $R=H$, $R_1=CH_2COOH$, $R_2=C_6H_5CO$; $R=$ pyrimidyl, $R_1=H$, $R_2=H$; $R=$ pyrimidyl, $R_1=CH_2COOH$, $R_2=H$; $R=$ 4-methyl pyrimidyl, $R_1=CH_2$, $R_2=C_6H_5CO$; $R=$ 4'-methyl pyrimidyl, $R_1=CH_2COOH$, $R_2=H$, are highly active against *S. aureus* compared to other compounds.

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Phytochemical Study of *Rumex acetosa* Linn.

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RUMEX acetosa Linn. (Polygonaceae) has been investigated earlier and oxalic, fumaric, α -ketoglutaric, succinic, glycolic, aconitic, citric and isocitric acids, naposide, a naphthalene glucoside², chrysophanic acid, chrysophanein have been isolated^{3,4}. We have reinvestigated the chemical constituents of the leaves, since these are used in homoeopathy.

Powdered leaves (50 g) were soaked in 60% ethanol (500 ml) for 24 hr. The alcohol was decanted and the solvent removed. The remaining concentrate, thus obtained, was extracted with chloroform (25 ml \times 3). The chloroform extract (A) was concentrated on water bath to 10 ml. To the aqueous layer, sulphuric acid (6 N; 50 ml) was added and refluxed for 30 min. After cooling, it was again extracted with chloroform (25 ml \times 3). The chloroform extract (B) was also concentrated to 10 ml. This was washed with distilled water (25 \times 2 ml) and the acid free chloroform layer was chromatographed.

The chloroform extracts A and B were chromatographed over silica gel G plate (200 μ ; 10 \times 20 cm) using benzene-ethyl acetate (8 : 2 v/v) as solvent. The plates were sprayed with 0.5% methanolic magnesium acetate. Three pink coloured spots appeared at R_f 0.60, 0.75 and 0.98 in case of the extract 'A'.

The three yellow coloured compounds were isolated from chloroform extract A by preparative thin layer chromatography on silica gel G and were characterized as chrysophanol, 1,8-dihydroxy anthraquinone and 1,8-dihydroxy 3-hydroxymethyl anthra-

quinone (aloe-emodin), respectively by comparison with the data (uv, ir) available in literature^{5,6}.

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Chemical Constituents of *Physalis peruviana* RootsMAHENDRA SAHAI* and PARTHA NEOGI¹Department of Organic Chemistry, The Weizmann Institute
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PHYSALIS peruviana Linn. (Solanaceae) is cultivated throughout India for its edible berries¹. The plant finds a variety of medicinal use in traditional system of medicine². The leaves of this plant yielded a number of withanolides³⁻⁷, physalin A⁸, perulactone⁹ and perulactone B⁹ while its roots yielded several new withanolides^{6,10} and tropane and secotropane alkaloids¹¹⁻¹⁴. The present communication reports the isolation of β -sitosterol, physalolactone, 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E, β -sitosterol-D-glucoside and rutin from the roots of this plant.

Experimental

Air-dried and powdered roots (2 kg) of *P. peruviana* were extracted with ethanol (95%). The ethanol extract was concentrated (1.0 l) and diluted with equal volume of water and then extracted successively with petrol (60-80°) and diethyl ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, evaporated to dryness and chromatographed over silica gel column.

Results and Discussion

β -Sitosterol: Elution of the column with benzene yielded β -sitosterol, shining needles, m.p. 136°

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